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SMARTDEST

CITIES AS MOBILITY HUBS:
TACKLING SOCIAL EXCLUSION THROUGH
SMART CITIZEN ENGAGEMENT

SmartDest

Task 3.3 - Report

Turin

Authors: Samantha Cenere, Loris Servillo

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Introduction

As shown through the analysis made in D3.2, student mobilities have been playing an increasingly relevant role in Turin's urban imaginary and in the growth strategies of the city. In the first case-study report on Turin included in D3.2, the investigation of the main trends of student mobilities and the identification of tensions, conflicts, and potential forms of exclusions directly and indirectly related to student mobilities has set the ground for the in-depth investigation of the case study carried out in T3.3 and T3.4.

As highlighted by the literature on the direct and indirect urban impacts of university student populations and as confirmed by circumstantial evidence in Turin, the pressure of student mobilities in the city could drive to three main negative outcomes: first, an increase in the share of the rental market for students in some areas; second, an increase in private investment in the student housing sector (PBSA); and third, the creation of retailscapes (especially nightlife ones) that cater almost exclusively to students (cf. Smith, 2005).

From this consideration descends that **student housing** represents a relevant dimension under various perspectives when we examine if, to what extent, and under which circumstances student mobilities exert a negative impact on long-term residents. Notably,

two main aspects of student housing may constitute potential drivers of social exclusion that could be detected through quantitative methods too: first, the spatial dynamics of student rental market (Hubbard, 2008; Munro et al., 2009; Munro & Livingston, 2012); and second, the investments in the PBSA real-estate market (Hubbard, 2009; Revington & August, 2020).

On the contrary, since previous research has proven quantitative methods are not useful to measure the extent to which an area is undergoing a retail transformation related to the supply of goods and services to students, this issue will be investigated only through qualitative methods in one of the 'hotspots' identified as particularly interesting to study how student mobilities may act as drivers of place transformation that exclude other groups (T 3.4).

The present report contains the results of quantitative analysis that provides evidence in support of the qualitative work that will be carried out in task 3.4. On the one hand, it focuses on the scope of student mobilities as either direct or indirect drivers of urban transformation and, eventually, social exclusion; on the other, the contains the results of a quantitative analysis of the vulnerability of the area that will be at the core of task 3.4. To do that, the report starts by providing a short overview of the issues identified in D3.2 and by describing the methodology employed in this task. Then, the presentation of results is divided in two main sections. The first section presents the results of the analysis of non-resident student dwellings concentration over the years in Turin to assess the scope of these mobilities; the second section tries to provide quantitative evidence on the vulnerability of a specific area of the city north of the Dora River. The area is of particular interest since it has been undergoing important transformations, of which the plans to make Turin a city increasingly attractive towards university students are a crucial component. Some considerations on the impact of Covid-19 on student housing in Turin follow.

Methodology

Few studies on studentification employ quantitative methods to measure the actual capacity of student mobilities to either trigger or accelerate processes of urban transformation. Those few studies usually focus on the number of students living in a certain area as a proxy of studentification issues, thus aiming mainly at assessing the

pressure of students on long-term residents' daily lives in studentified neighbourhoods by measuring students' dwellings concentration.

The quantitative analysis of student pressure presents two main methodological concerns: first, student housing morphology presents relevant geographical differences due to the local specificities of student accommodation (e.g., HMOs in the UK context versus shared flats in blocks in Southern Europe); and second, the availability of data on student population is deeply affected by the local regulative framework (see Hochstenbach et al., 2020 for a case in which municipal registers provide useful data to analyse student private-rental housing market). This last issue is crucial, since in Italy, on the one hand, it is not mandatory for people moving to a city to enrol in Higher Education to register as residents and, on the other, local statistical offices at city level collect data exclusively on the resident population. These difficulties may result in a methodological preference for qualitative research (Garmendia et al., 2012; Prada, 2019).

To overcome this methodological difficulty and try to provide some preliminary quantitative evidence of the phenomenon, we drew from those studies that employ university enrolment data on student residence (see for example Sage et al., 2012).

We contacted the two main public universities of the city (namely, the University of Turin and the Polytechnic University of Turin) and asked for the enrolment data of all students from the academic year 2010/2011 to the current one (2020/2021). Due to the size of the two universities' databases (more than 900,000 records for Unito and more than 360,000 for Polito), we then selected four target years (2010/2011, 2013/2014, 2017/2018, and 2020/2021) per each institution. In order to select only those students that moved to Turin to study, we selected those who took up domicile in Turin but were not resident in the city. To distinguish between international students and students who were born and/or have grown up in Turin but do not have an Italian citizenship, we selected only those whose country of birth was not Italy.

However, the actual database employed does not cover the whole non-resident student population in Turin. Indeed, due to the fact that the databases of the two universities are made of the information that students provide when they enrol in a university course, the information contained present many inconsistencies, missing or partial information, and errors. Moreover, some Italian extra-Piedmont students may still commute to Turin and/or being enrolled in courses in which attending classes is not mandatory. Therefore, the final database used contained on average correct information on 10,000 students per

each academic year, representing around a quarter of the non-resident student population (Italian extra-Piedmont and non-Italian extra-Piedmont) reported by official statistics.

To assess students' pressure on the different areas of the city, we first mapped where non-resident students lived in Turin and then aggregated those point in both the 92 statistical zones of the city and its 23 neighbourhoods. The result are four maps, one per academic year, that represent students' concentration in each statistical zone and other four maps that represent students' concentration in each neighbourhood. We considered both students renting a flat and student living in either a PBSA or a public university residence.

We also wanted to see if and how students' concentration has changed over time and if some areas have become more attractive than others over the years. To do that, we represented the variation of student concentration in statistical zones from 2010/2011 to 2017/2018. We decided not to use the academic year 2020/2021 as the last target year to measure the evolution of student concentration since student housing dynamics were deeply affected by the spread of the Covid pandemic.

On the contrary, there is no evidence in the literature of attempts to assess through quantitative methods and cartographic representation the role of student mobilities with regards to multiple dimensions of social exclusion. In order to cope with this methodological void, we pursued two complementary paths.

In order to provide preliminary evidence of the social, economic, and demographic vulnerability of the area in which the 'hotspots' that are going to be investigated through qualitative methods in T3.4 are located, we used some basic sociodemographic indicators retrieved from different sources. Namely, we gathered data from the Census statistical survey (2011), sociodemographic data from the City's Statistical Office (figures: various years; maps: 2018), data on households and individuals' income at sub-city level from Agenzia delle Entrate (2019), and real-estate data from the national Real-Estate Market Observatory (OMI).

Unfortunately, the City's Statistical Office does not collect many relevant data that are instead part of the Census statistical survey, such as the ones on the number of households renting their dwelling or the share of houses that are either empty or occupied by non-residents persons. These data would be extremely useful, on the one hand, to measure the share of flats that have been removed from the traditional rental market to be instead rented to students and, on the other, to provide a proxy of the

share of flats that are rented to students and other non-resident individuals. Thus, the scope of studentification processes related to the presence of student flats has been assessed only through an analysis of the spatial dynamics of student dwellings' concentration, rather than through the comparison between the variation of the number of students having their domicile in the area and the variation in households renting their dwelling in the same area. The topic will be therefore explored through qualitative research.

Networking activity made to gather data:

- Statistical office of the City of Turin (public data and few non-public data)
- OMI (nothing more than the data publicly available on the website)
- Real estate agencies that conduct research too (Gabetti, Furbatto – not available)
- UPPI (not available)
- Student housing platforms (Housing Anywhere, Cerco Alloggio – not available for data, but CercoAlloggio will take part in interviews; TurinHouse – some doubts on the accountability of the platform)
- Turismo Torino e Provincia (not really useful for us)
- University and Polytechnic (various data on student population over the last 10 years, particularly useful to map where non-resident and international students live in Turin)
- ISTAT (public data)
- Immobiliare.it (public data)
- Osservatorio Regionale per il Diritto allo Studio (public data)
- Agenzia delle Entrate (data on income at submunicipal level for 2019)

Chapter 1. Student mobilities in Turin: spatial distribution

Figure 1

As shown in D3.2, Turin has been experiencing a rapid growth of its student population since the beginning of 2000s (fig. 2). Part of this growth is due to an increased capacity of both the city and its Higher Education institutions to be attractive for both students coming from other Italian regions and international students.

Figure 2

The increased of this mobile population is particularly significant when compared to the relentless demographic contraction of the city, which has undergone a 2% decrease. Notably, in the years that followed the 2008 economic crisis, the city has lost more than 37,000 residents, passing from more than 908,000 in 2007 to 872,316 in 2019 (fig. 2). In the same years, the number of Italian and international non-resident students enrolled at both the University and the Polytechnic amounted to 31,000 (figures for the academic year 2018/2019. Source: Stanchi, 2020).

Figure 3

Albeit the demographic contraction of Turin is evenly distributed across almost all the neighbourhoods, the decrease is particularly evident in some areas of the city. In particular, the neighbourhoods Cenisia (-8,7%) and Aurora (-9,2%) seem to have experienced the most severe demographic contraction (figg. 4 and 5). The only exception is the city Centre, which is the only neighbourhood presenting a positive demographic trend (+4,7%), followed by the small and rich neighbourhood Madonna del Pilone (+0,6%). However, to investigate the reason of this demographic change using quantitative methods and to assess if there could be a correlation with student housing trends, additional data should be collected, such as the number of residents died over the period considered in the neighbourhood and the number of residents who moved from the neighbourhood over the same period.

RESIDENTS VARIATION PER NEIGHBOURHOOD (2011, 2014, 2018, 2020)

Source: City of Turin's Statistical Office

Residents per neighbourhood
(absolute numbers)

Figure 4

DEMOGRAPHIC TREND (2011-2020)

Source: City of Turin's Statistical Office

Variation of population per neighbourhood (%)

Figure 5

On the contrary, figures on non-resident student population show an opposite trend, both in general terms and with regards to the neighbourhood scale. In general, the maps on student dwellings' concentration highlight that where non-resident students decide to live is highly dependent on the proximity to a university building (figg. 6 from to 11), as

confirmed by the recent work of Zasina and colleagues (2021: 15), according to which 'the students' residential geographies span almost the entire inner-city area'.

In the academic year 2010/2011, the neighbourhoods that registered the highest non-resident student concentration were the ones close to the main university branches, such as the City Centre (for the University of Turin), and Cenisia, Crocetta, and San Salvario (for the Polytechnic) (fig. 6). When we zoom in and focus on the concentration of students at the level of the statistical zones, it is possible to appreciate that the areas registering the highest student concentration in 2010/2011 were Cenisia and Crocetta sud, two areas close to Polytechnic's headquarter (fig. 7). In these areas, figures show that 450 non-resident students on average from our database lived in each of them.

Figure 6

Figure 7

The map of students' concentration in the academic year 2013/2014 shows that Cenisia and Crocetta sud experienced a further rise in student population, with the statistical

zone between the neighbourhoods Cenisia and San Paolo (the one coloured in dark red) increasing non-resident student population by more than 30% (fig. 8). At the neighbourhood scale, the areas already attractive to students in 2011 increased their student population, with the neighbourhood Crocetta at the top of the list (more than 1,100 non-resident students from the database), followed by the city Centre, Cenisia, and San Salvario (fig. 9).

Figure 8

Figure 9

The maps covering the academic year 2017/2018 are particularly relevant with regards to the area of interest, since they allow to appreciate the urban transformation triggered by the opening of both the University's Campus Luigi Einaudi-CLE (2012) and the Institute of Applied Art and Design-IAAD (2013), located in the North-East part of the city, on the Dora riverbank. Indeed, the map shows that the areas in the immediate proximity of the CLE became increasingly appealing for non-resident students. Borgo Rossini, the Gasometro-CLE area, and Borgata Aurora (on the Dora's North riverbank) and Borgo

Dora-Valdocco and Vanchiglia (on the Dora's South riverbank) experienced a significant shift towards becoming studentified areas. (fig. 10). Notably, with regards to the student population database employed (see Methodology section), non-resident students living in the small area of Borgo Rossini passed from being 66 in 2010/2011 to 140 in 2017/2018, thus almost doubling over the years. The adjacent areas of Vanchiglia and Borgata Aurora experienced a similar transformation, passing respectively from 290 to 447 students and from 125 to 214 students.

However, in absolute values, both maps show that Cenisia continued to be the most attractive area for non-resident students (with figures double than Vanchiglia), followed by Crocetta Sud (fig. 10).

Figure 10

Zooming out at the scale of the former 23 neighbourhoods of the city, the map shows that Aurora and Vanchiglia (the two areas respectively on the north and on the south of the Dora River and in the immediate proximity of the new university branches) have been increasingly populated by non-resident students (fig. 11). Vanchiglia passed from 454 students in 2010/2011 to 759 students seven years later, while Aurora passed from 344 to 611 students.

STUDENTS CONCENTRATION (2017-2018)

Figure 11

In order to better assess to what extent high students' concentration constitutes a demographic issue for the neighbourhood, we compared it with the total amount of residents in the same neighbourhood and look at the variation of these figures in the period 2011-2018 (fig. 12). First, we calculated the number of residents per one student in 2011 and in 2018. Then, calculated the variation between these numbers¹. The map shows that the areas close to the main HE headquarters and where new PBSAs are located are the ones that, during the years, experienced an increase in the pressure of students over the resident populations. Considering the sample at our disposal, the number of residents per one non-resident student decreased by 50% in San Paolo and by 47% in Aurora.

¹ With regards to the proportion between students and residents, a methodological clarification is needed. Indeed, while the number of residents per neighbourhood is correct, it should be kept in mind that the figures regarding non-resident students come from the database we built using the enrolment data provided by Unito and Polito. As specified in the introduction, the database we obtained contains a fourth of the amount of Italian and non-Italian non resident students reported by official statistics (see for example IRES, March 2021), according to which this population amounts to 40,000 students. However, besides the fact that some records in the database were lost due to missing information, figures usually reported do not take into account the fact that some extra-Piedmont students may not take up domicile in Turin and consider as 'foreigner students' simply every student who does not have an Italian citizenship.

VARIATION OF STUDENT/RESIDENTS RATIO (2011-2018)

Variation of number of residents per 1 student (%)

- 50 - -39
- 39 - -18
- 18 - 16
- 16 - 45
- 45 - 68
- 68 - 135

Figure 12

Chapter 2. Potential social costs of student pressure in Turin. A focus on the Dora's North riverbank

Figure 13

The aim of this section is to focus on the area north of the river Dora, since this part of the city has been undergoing profound transformations, both directly connected to the increased attractiveness of Turin towards university students and broader urban transformations. Indeed, rather than focussing on an area on which the social costs of the pressure exerted by mobile populations are already evident, we identified this area because the attempt to transform it into a student destination is part of a larger project of urban renewal that sees the attraction of students and other mobile populations an asset for the requalification of a particularly fragile area.

To provide evidence of the fact that this area is characterised by a higher degree of social, economic, and demographic vulnerability compared to other areas in the city which have undergone similar processes in terms of student concentration and investments on infrastructures for students, we have identified some indicators coming from the Census statistical survey 2011, the City's Statistical Office yearly database, and the Italian Real-Estate Market Observatory (OMI).

Recent research has already highlighted how the neighbourhood that goes under the name of Aurora (which comprehends Borgata Aurora, Borgo Dora-Valdocco, and Borgo Rossini) is particularly fragmented inside (fig. 13). Indeed, the eastern area corresponding to Borgo Rossini (the purple one in the map) presents a different socio-economic and demographic profile compared to the western part of the neighbourhood, which is the one currently identified with Aurora (the blue one) (AuroraLab, 2020). Nevertheless, both the previous section and the evidence reported in D3.2 have shown that the whole area has become increasingly attractive for both non-resident students and political and economic interests related to student mobilities (i.e., opening of new student accommodation facilities, renting of apartments to students, student retailscape). Thus, focussing on different indicators it is possible to highlight the specific vulnerability of the area in which each "hotspot" is located with regards to various forms of social exclusion. According to the 2018 demographic data, Borgo Rossini is characterised by a higher old-age index compared to the western part of the neighbourhood (fig. 14). The high percentage of the old-age index in this area is particularly relevant when we consider, on the one hand, the need for hospitals and health centres and, on the other, the potential greater disruption that could be provoked by the transformation of the local retailscape through the opening of retail activities that cater mainly to young people and foster the birth of a nightlife playscape in the area. As the preliminary research on the area has

shown (D3.2), Borgo Rossini hosts two of the “hotspots” that are particularly important for the investigation of exclusionary dynamics driven by student mobilities in Turin; namely, the project of converting the former Maria Adelaide hospital in a student residence and the *mala movida* issue in the main square of Borgo Rossini.

OLD-AGE INDEX in DISTRICT 7 (2018)

Source: City of Turin's Statistical Office

Ratio between resid. aged >65 and resid. aged <14 (%)

Figure 14

On the other hand, Aurora is the most fragile area of the city with regards to various socioeconomic indicators but at the same time it is also an area in which various urban regeneration projects have been launched.

Aurora is characterised by the highest rate of foreign residents in the city (fig. 15) and severe economic vulnerability (fig. 16). Notably, a large part of Aurora's residents have an income between 0 and 10,000 euros, while at the same time the area is characterised by an average taxable income extremely low (less than 20,000 euros).

SHARE OF FOREIGN RESIDENTS in DISTRICT 7 (2018)

Source: City of Turin's Statistical Office

Figure 15

ECONOMIC VULNERABILITY 2019

Source: Agenzia delle Entrate 2019

Taxable Income from 0 to 10.000 euros (frequency)

Average taxable income (euros)

Figure 16

With regards to housing ownership, the area presents figures in line with the majority of other parts of the city, with a share of residents between 28% and 36% renting their dwelling (fig. 17).

HOUSEHOLDS RENTING THEIR DWELLING 2011

Source: Census 2011

Houselds renting their dwelling (% on total)

Figure 17

The housing stock is characterised by a poor state of conservation (fig. 18) and a high degree of empty houses, both in absolute values and compared to the totality of the housing stock in the area (fig. 19 and 20). More than 1,500 houses resulted empty during the 2011 Census, corresponding to the 13% of the total.

BUILDINGS IN POOR STATE OF CONSERVATION (2011)

Source: Census 2011

Buildings in poor state of conservation (% on total)

Figure 18

EMPTY HOUSES PER NEIGHBOURHOOD (2011)

Source: Census 2011

Empty houses (absolute numbers)

Figure 19

SHARE OF EMPTY HOUSES PER NEIGHBOURHOOD (2011)

Source: Census 2011

Empty houses (% on total)

Figure 20

Figures of the real estate market show that Borgo Rossini and Aurora present different dynamics with regards to housing prices variation (fig. 21 and 22). In 2018, the average price per square meter for a property in Borgo Rossini was more than 2,600 euros. These figures are starkly different from the ones of Aurora, in which instead the average price corresponded to less than half Borgo Rossini's prices (1,200 euros/sqm).

While the whole housing market in Turin was severely affected by the 2008 economic crisis, the two areas shown different trends with regards to the evolution of housing prices from 2008 to 2018. Borgo Rossini shows a decrease of 2.6%, while in Aurora housing prices dropped by more than 33%.

HOUSE PRICES 2018

Source: OMI

House price (euro per sqm)

- 1070 - 1562
- 1562 - 2151
- 2151 - 2891
- 2891 - 3620
- 3620 - 4646

Figure 21

HOUSE PRICES VARIATION (2008-2018)

Source: OMI

House prices variation (%)

- 50 - -40
- 40 - -30
- 30 - -20
- 20 - 0
- 0 - 10
- 10 - 20

Figure 22

Chapter 3. Covid-19 disruptions

In the academic year 2020/2021, despite the data on the enrolment to the two main HE institutions of the city registered an unexpected increase, many students either decided to leave the city or were not able to come to Turin to study. The impact on the overall Turin's student rental market is reflected by the amount of available rooms to rent, which increased by 108% in 2020 (source: Immobiliare.it). In Spring 2021, figures on Turin's student rental market shown an even worse situation, reporting an increase by 139% of the rooms available for rent (source: Soloaffitti.it). This trend was accompanied by a corresponding general decrease in prices, which registered a -6% (around 17 euros less) for a single room and -15% for a shared room (source: Soloaffitti.it).

However, the general decrease in the student population physically present in Turin over the last year was evenly distributed across the city (fig. 23 and 24), since the map is almost identical to the one of 2017/2018. The only exception seems to be represented by the most peripheral areas in the Western part of Turin.

2020/2021

Figure 23

STUDENTS CONCENTRATION (2020 - 2021)

Figure 24

During the current academic year, the city will have to face an uncertain situation: will the ongoing possibility to attend classes online prevent students to move to Turin or the performance of the student rental market will go back to a pre-Covid situation?

Conclusions

The quantitative analysis conducted allowed to provide further evidence of the uneven socio-spatial impact that student mobilities exert in the city of Turin. This impact is understood as both a direct one (i.e., concentration of students' dwellings in specific areas) and an indirect one (i.e., real-estate investment in PBSAs in areas that are characterised by a higher degree of demographic and socioeconomic vulnerability).

The analysis on the concentration of non-resident students' dwellings and its evolution over the last ten years shows how the distribution of students is highly dependent on the proximity to a university branch. Thus, the opening of a new university building constitutes an important element of urban transformation whose consequences at the neighbourhood scale have to be anticipated. Needless to say, the opening of new student residences represents a very specific kind of intervention that exerts a stronger pressure on the area interested by this transformation.

On the other hand, the focus on Dora's north riverbank indicates that the area is one of the most vulnerable parts of the city with regards to many social, economic, and

demographic indicators. The aim of this analysis was not to provide a picture of the exclusionary effects already unfolded due to urban transformations related to increased student mobilities. Rather, the investigation allowed to point out multiple dimensions that could translate into forms of social exclusion (such as, housing exclusion, place transformation, exclusion from public space) if processes of urban transformation related to student mobilities are not managed keeping in mind the specific fragility of these areas. This kind of analytical work is particularly relevant especially if we consider that the ultimate goal of SMARTDEST consists in developing CityLabs as participatory fora that eventually aim at informing local policies in order to provide an alternative approach to the government of cities as mobility hubs. In order to provide further and in-depth evidence of both the current and potential exclusionary effects of student mobilities in Turin, these results will be complemented by the qualitative analysis conducted for T3.4 and the engagement of the stakeholders.

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